

Federated Persistent Data Repository Approach for FIBRE multi-CMF Testbed

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Abstract—A Network for Experimentation (NfExp) is typically a regional, national, or specialized international testbed like GENI, PlanetLab, and OFELIA that are developed to support the experimentation of new protocols, services and applications mostly in the context of Future Internet (FI). In effect, a Network for Experimentation allows an experimenter to configure, instantiate, run, and collect measurements of distributed experiments on top of a real testbed managed by a Control and Monitoring Framework (CMF). Currently available CMFs developments are directly or indirectly service-oriented architectures focused, as an example, on wired or wireless networks research domains. A new approach for the Network for Experimentation considered in this paper is the FIBRE multi-CMF testbed. In FIBRE, various existing CMFs are integrated to achieve a broader set of supported applications and service domains. Among the technical challenges involved in the multi-CMF approach, this paper describes the approach adopted for the persistent data repository necessary to store the monitored and collected experimental data. An iRODS-based federated monitoring persistent data repository proposal is presented for the FIBRE multi-CMF testbed. The solution adopts a standardized monitoring data format and representation whenever possible. It is a transparent data storage facility among multiple native DBMS, with persistent monitoring data access and retrieval, and a high-level monitoring data integration.

Index Terms—Monitoring; Data Repository; iRODS; FIBRE; Testbed; Network for Experimentation; Control and Monitoring Framework; multi-CMF; Federation.

1 INTRODUCTION AND MOTIVATION

Network for Experimentation (NfExp) are testbeds that are developed to support the experimentation of new protocols, services and applications. NfExp allows an experimenter to configure, instantiate, run, and collect measurements of distributed experiments on top of a testbed managed by a Control and Monitoring Framework (CMF).

Networks for Experimentation have been widely deployed around the world, mostly by academic research projects. Apart from this, major networking and technology companies are deeply involved with network experimentation and are using software-defined networking (SDN) solutions in their labs, their products, and eventually in their in-

frastructure. As an example, Google has announced that it is using SDN and OpenFlow for interconnecting its datacenter and WAN links considering traffic engineering issues [1] [2]. In effect, innovative development needs several experiments to run in testbeds to guarantee a trustable deployment on a service network. Organizations have essential concerns in jeopardizing their multi-million dollar business without proper validation, tests, deployment, measurements, and a certain level of confidence that any new development requires. This emphasizes the importance of having networks for experimentation, also mentioned as *testbeds* to run network experiments. As such, NfExp helps to develop new technologies like SDN approaches, OpenFlow, or any other new service or protocol [3].

The network for experimentation or testbed has a Control and Monitoring Framework (CMF) that controls and monitors all NfExp operations. The CMF deals with critical issues such as resource orchestration, federation, access control, performance, availability, instrumentation and monitoring support, multi-CMF integration, and operation, to men-

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tion a few [3].

Regarding CMFs, several solutions are being deployed worldwide, such as Global Environment for Network Innovation (GENI) [4], ProtoGENI [5], PlanetLab [6], OpenFlow in Europe Linking Infrastructures and Applications (OFELIA) [7] and Orbit Management Framework (OMF) [8]. Each CMF aims at solving a handful of problems, oriented to their research focus like wired, wireless, or optical, as examples [9].

Considering a multi-CMF infrastructure involving multiple institutions, they all could benefit from code reuse, different application usage, a myriad of users, foster innovation among different communities towards Future Internet architecture, industry adoption and funding, and market ramp-up. In a nutshell, a multi-CMF context promotes integration and collaboration among universities and industries from different countries around the world.

Multi-CMF infrastructure deployments pose multiple challenges and technical issues. Problems such as multi-CMF federation, experiment instrumentation and orchestration, security policy, and experiment persistent data storage are examples [10].

This paper presents an approach for the experiment's persistent data storage in a multi-CMF infrastructure. Each control and monitoring framework already has its own persistent or temporary experiment data approach. Nonetheless, in infrastructures with several CMFs, this standalone approach may not be suitable for a global experiment with multiple measurement points collecting data in different locations.

In this context, we present a Federated Persistent Data Repository approach for the FIBRE multi-CMF testbed. With this approach, the experimenter has a single point of reference to store, access, and retrieve data without having to worry about where to access it.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the proposed multi-CMF persistent monitoring data integration approach. Section III presents the FIBRE¹ (Future Internet Brazilian environment for Experimentation) multi-CMF testbed, and section IV presents the iRODS architecture. Section V presents the use case of persistent data integration with iRODS in the FIBRE multi-CMF testbed, and section VI presents

the iRODS naming and federation deployments. Finally, section VII presents the final considerations.

2 MULTI-CMF PERSISTENT MONITORING DATA INTEGRATION APPROACH

In different existing CMFs, the collected monitoring parameters are processed to allow two distinct functionalities:

- Data visualization through, typically, web portal; and
- Persistent experiment data storage.

For on-the-fly web access and viewing, most CMFs process the monitored experiment data according to a specific data representation and format standard and display the real-time monitored data to the experimenter (user). In terms of the permanent storage functionality, the monitoring parameters are stored in a specific database management system (DBMS), which is, in fact, a CMF implementation choice.

As such, the multi-CMF persistent monitoring data integration approach can be achieved by decomposing the monitoring operations in different steps, such as:

- CMF Monitoring Data Format and Representation;
- CMF Seamless Data Storage;
- CMF Monitoring Data Retrieval and Visualization; and
- CMF Data Federation.

The CMF Monitoring Data Format and Representation step correspond to the problem of publishing the measurement data in a standardized way. The visualization tools available at the multi-CMF framework can easily retrieve and display this data to the user. This standardization is necessary since each CMF stores its measurement data in a proprietary format, usually not compatible with other CMFs, making the process of interpreting all these different data formats difficult, costly, and error-prone.

CMF Seamless Data Storage treats the fact that each CMF stores its data using its storage methodology. Therefore, retrieving the stored data from all of them implies having a specific method for each CMF used and in knowing where the stored data is. This represents an important issue, analyzing from the perspective of deployment and maintenance. It would be necessary to develop a set of tools for each CMF to have access to this distributed data. Aiming

1. FIBRE project is co-funded by the Brazilian Council for Scientific and Technological Development (CNPq) and by the European Commission within its Seventh Framework Program.

at simplifying data storage, the federated persistent data repository approach proposes a way to store and access experiment result data from any CMF in a single point of reference. Instead of having each CMF measurement data stored just at its database, the goal is to store all experiment result data at a distributed file storage system, whenever needed or demanded by the experimenter.

Storing all data in a seamless storage facility allows working with a less complex methodology to access the data. It alleviates the pressure from the experimenter in having to know where all data is stored. All of them can be accessed using the same set of tools, solving the CMF Monitoring Data Access. This set of tools (GUI or CLI) has to be used on the client-side, independently of which data will be accessed.

Having in mind the necessity of accessing multi-CMF monitoring data among different domains brings up the problem of CMF Data Federation. Each domain will have its own CMFs persistent data repository, which will be connected to other domains repositories. All of this interconnection needs to be transparent for reading and writing data.

To achieve full transparency and integration, the federated persistent data repository approach proposes an open-source solution to the problems mentioned above, providing a reliable, scalable, secure, multi-platform solution to the multi-CMF experiment data persistent storage.

3 THE FIBRE MULTI-CMF TESTBED

The FIBRE Project [11] develops a Network for Experimentation (NfExp) involving Brazil and Europe, with the primary objective of supporting research on the Future Internet (FI) [12]. The inter-continental network infrastructure is composed of a FIBRE backbone in Brazil (FIBRE-BRnet), another in Europe (FIBRE-EUnet), and islands networks. The FIBRE network in Brazil, which is the focus of this development, interconnects ten institutions (aka island) in Brazil, and FIBRE-EUnet interconnects three institutions in Europe. RNP [13] and GEANT [14] will be, respectively, their interconnection backbone network (Figure 1).

A typical Brazilian island uses Icarus nodes, OpenFlow switches, a Top Of Rack (ToR) switch, netFPGA servers, and regular servers using virtualization for shared services (authentication, name services, infrastructure monitoring, and data storage) and a border router (Figure 2).

Fig. 1. FIBRE-BRnet and FIBRE-EUnet interconnection [11]

Fig. 2. Basic FIBRE island infrastructure [11]

All these resources compose the necessary infrastructure shared by three different control and monitoring frameworks (CMFs) in FIBRE islands: OFELIA Control Framework, cOntrol and Management Framework (OMF), and ProtoGENI [15].

The FIBRE Instrumentation and Measurement (I&M) Architecture (FIBRE I&M) corresponds to the *monitoring* part of the FIBRE multi-CMF. It has, as an essential requirement, the capability to configure, monitor, collect, and display both infrastructure and experiment specific monitoring data for distinct federated or individual CMF aggregates in the FIBRE-BRnet context [10].

One of the architecture building blocks of the FIBRE IM is a persistent data repository that aims at allowing users to store and retrieve data from their own or others previous experiments according

to their access privileges [9].

Taking into account that FIBRE islands will host multiple-CMF and eventually will use resources from each of them in a federated infrastructure, several architectural I&M issues arise. Among these, there is measurement data storage. As indicated by the problem decomposition discussed in section II, the measurement data storage requires a solution for various steps (data format, seamless data storage, data access, other). As such, we develop a solution based on iRODS [16] that is flexible, data format-agnostic, provides access control, and supports federation. The following sections will further discuss iRODS concerning these issues and how it fits as the basic block for the FIBRE data persistent repository component in its I&M architecture.

4 THE iRODS ARCHITECTURE

iRODS is a data grid system that aims at consolidating data systems [17]. The adoption of iRODS in the FIBRE I&M Architecture was motivated by the fact that its components and functionalities meet most of the FIBRE IM requirements for persistent data storage. This software provides a way to manage, organize, share, protect, and preserve data among users. Based on a hierarchical structure, it is possible to build a transparent storage solution (centralized or distributed) that looks from the final user perspective just as a regular directory.

The iRODS architecture is built upon three main components, as shown in Figure 3, namely:

- 1) iRODS Metadata Catalog (iCAT), which is a catalog that stores descriptive metadata information for the data stored in the iRODS Data Server in some DBMS. It is useful to track data in the iRODS system.
- 2) iRODS server, which is a software that interacts with the access protocol of a specific storage system, enables storing and sharing of data geographically distributed and spans distinct administrative domains.
- 3) Clients, which is a set of tools to access and manage data in the iRODS server [18].

Another feature of iRODS is the concept of *zone*. An iRODS zone is an independent iRODS system (an iCAT-enabled host, possibly other non-iCAT Servers or iRODS server, and clients) that can interoperate with different separate iRODS Zones through a federation scheme [19].

The application of these iRODS capabilities in the FIBRE context is presented next as a use case.

Fig. 3. iRODS architecture

5 PERSISTENT DATA INTEGRATION WITH iRODS IN FIBRE MULTI-CMF - A USE CASE

iRODS was elected to support the solution for the persistent data storage system in FIBRE I&M multi-CMF framework (Figure 4).

iRODS main characteristics include its open-source BSD license, its ability to enable collaboration, its flexibility, a stable solution with more than 12 years of deployments, its scalability and the possibility to integrate to external cloud solutions such as Amazon AWS [20]. Beyond that, iRODS main features include capabilities such as:

- To manage distributed collections of data;
- To maintain a metadata catalog;
- To apply policy management at each storage location;
- To audit the application policies; and
- To federate with other data grids.

In the FIBRE I&M architecture, each experiment will generate its measurement data set in one of the CMFs adopted using a monitoring tool. The Measurement Data Integration Point (MDIP) (Figure 4) will provide an interface to transfer the raw data to the persistent data repository. It will also provide a standardized interface that can be used by the visualization and portal services of the I&M architecture to access data in real-time whenever possible or in the *post-mortem*.

To provide access control to the experiment data, each user (experimenter) will have access to two iRODS resources: a private and a public one. A resource is a logical mapping to where the monitored data is stored. When it is created, it is necessary

Fig. 4. Multi-CMF iRODS persistent storage in FIBRE IM Architecture

to define its type (Unix file system, windows file system, other), it's class (cache, archive, other), and the host and directory where the data is stored. By default, the data will be stored in the private resource, and it is up to the experimenter to make it public.

The user will be able to access his measurement data using the Visualization and Portal Services, which can be both I&M Web Portal or iRODS clients. The first one is useful when the user needs a unified, intuitive, and easy-to-understand view of the experiment measurement data, made possible by the standardized interfaces provided by the MDIP services. The second option, iRODS clients, is useful when the user wants to access the raw measurement data, process it, and interpret it using his/her tools or methodologies.

In effect, iRODS currently has four clients [18]

[10]:

- iRODS Web Browser;
- iRODS Explorer;
- iDrop; and
- iCommands.

They are not mutually exclusive, and they may work rather complementary. iDROP and iRODS web browser are web interfaces that are integrated with the I&M Web Portal, to provide access to the persistent data repository. iRODS explorer is a Microsoft(R) Windows(R) tool very similar to the well-known Windows Explorer, and iCommands is a command-line tool that works both in Windows and Linux environments.

In the FIBRE multi-CMF framework, each CMF has its particularity to create an experiment and to monitor it. We will explain now how iRODS will work with each CMF and consider its specificities.

In the OFELIA Control Framework (OCF), the implementation adopted consists in having at each virtual machine instantiated by the experimenter, in a slice, an iRODS iCommands. This instantiated iCommand is part of MDIP services.

In the OFELIA CMF management interface, after creating a slice, you will have to associate the resources to it, such as OpenFlow switches, ports, VLANs, and virtual machines. Each virtual machine comes with a customized Operating System (OS) installed, based on a template OS image created by the OCF administrators. To support the persistent data storage, a new OS image is produced with iRODS iCommands client pre-configured with zone information, local iCAT name server, and some environment variables. As such, at the end of the experiment, the user will be able to use MDIP services to send the measured data to the persistent data repository directly.

In the Orbit Monitoring Framework (OMF), the experiment life-cycle has three steps. Firstly, the user will submit his/her experiment through the Experiment Controller (EC). The EC communicates with the Aggregate Manager (AM), which starts the experiment and sends all measured data to the OML Server (OML) (Figure 4). For this specific CMF, the iRODS iCommands client is an MDIP service in the EC interface. The EC, in turn, will have access to the OML Server to retrieve the experiment results. From that point on, the experimenter will have the option to store them in the FIBRE I&M Persistent Data Repository.

Last but not least, in ProtoGENI (PGENI), measurements are performed by Measurement Points (MP) within the user slice, and stored at a particular node called Global Node (GN) also within the slice. Alongside with other MDIP services, an iRODS client is installed on the GN to send the measurement data to the persistent data repository.

6 IRODS NAMING AND FEDERATION ISSUES

The scenario discussed until now was focused on the solution required for a single FIBRE island defining how to collect, store, and visualize its monitored data. In effect, FIBRE I&M adopts a solution for multi-CMF data integration, and, as such, a federation strategy is required. iRODS plays a role and contributes to the federation schema, as discussed next.

The iRODS contribution to the federation scheme adopted includes:

- A *naming* scheme; and

- An *iRODS zone* delimiting administrative scheme.

A well-defined structure for naming the monitoring data in iRODS is needed to store it in the persistent repository. This feature enhances a seamless experience for the experimenter and facilitates administrative tasks.

FIBRE I&M naming scheme supports FIBRE's diversified infrastructure, which is composed of various islands on different physical locations and multiples CMFs. The naming scheme supports transparent access to persistent data. The pattern for the logical name-space is as follows:

/institution/user/file-name-experimentation

Using iRODS zones, we create a federated-like persistent data repository structure. In FIBRE I&M, the default is to keep the monitored data residing at the local zone in which it was generated. Through iRODS federation-like administrative zones (mapping FIBRE island to iRODS zone), the experimenter can share data among islands. Experimenter and user access privileges are defined to allow access and to prevent unauthorized tasks. The authorization and authentication system adopted by FIBRE is a conjunction of an LDAP (Lightweight Directory Access Protocol) schema and an identity federation (CAFe) [21].

The logical name-space is the abstraction of a physical path and name of a specific chunk of monitored data generated by an experiment. The process of mapping the logical name to the physical path and name is done by the metadata facility supported by the iCAT server. Therefore if the data moves from one resource to another resource, it would be unnoticed to the user and infrastructure-independent.

Figure 5 illustrates the adopted scheme with three federated islands: island 1, island 2, and island 3. Each of them will store the experiments data of their testbeds and will catalog them on its iRODS iCAT.

In general, zone access privileges will be managed by the federated LDAP/CAFe system mentioned before. Accessing data in the original zone is represented in Figure 5 as real communication. Clients will also be able to query for data stored in other trusted zones, through a virtual connection using iRODS mechanism. If the data is not stored at its original zone, the multiple iRODS iCAT will communicate among them to locate it. Regarding

Fig. 5. Multi-CMF iRODS Federation

monitoring data visualization, the iRODS Clients will also access data repositories in local or remote islands/zones.

7 FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

A federated persistent monitoring data repository approach based on iRODS for the FIBRE multi-CMF testbed was presented. The approach allows monitoring data integration by the FIBRE instrumentation and monitoring facility leading to seamless data storage while maintaining the native CMF's databases and repositories for local storage. Monitoring data access and retrieval also make use of the iRODS-based facility developed, allowing the federation of multiple FIBRE islands through a simple naming scheme and management defined administrative zones based on iRODS iCAT metadata.

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